

Ambitions, Realities, and Challenges

Insights on Harmonised EU Procedures from the EFFORTS Project

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Over the last two decades, the development of European Union (hereinafter also ‘EU’) rules on judicial cooperation in civil and commercial matters has given rise to a vast and somewhat intricate network of instruments aimed at facilitating cross-border debt recovery. In very broad strokes, these instruments can be divided into two separate categories, depending on the specific purpose pursued by the legislation in question.

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Within the first category, it is possible to classify Regulations whose purpose is to allow the circulation of domestic enforcement titles across Member States. This category includes, of course, the Brussels I bis Regulation¹ and the Regulation on the European Enforcement Order (hereinafter ‘EEO’),² both of which allow for the direct enforcement abroad of national titles issued pursuant to domestic proceedings. The second category, by contrast, includes instruments which were set up by the EU legislature with a view to allowing creditors to pursue the recovery of cross-border claims on the basis of harmonised European procedures instead than resorting to national redress mechanisms. It is this second category, which includes the European Payment Order (‘EPO’),³ the European Small Claims Procedure (‘ESCP’),⁴ and the European Account Preservation Order (‘EAPO’)⁵ Regulations, which will be the exclusive focus of this contribution.

More specifically, the aim of this paper is to share some practical insights collected during EFFORTS (hereinafter, also the ‘EFFORTS Project’ or simply the ‘Project’),⁶ a comparative research project funded by the Justice Programme of the European Union and conducted by an international Consortium comprising the Max Planck Institute Luxembourg and the Universities of Milan, Heidelberg, Brussels VUB, Vilnius, and Zagreb. Over the course of two years, the Consortium members analysed the state of implementation of five European Regulations on the cross-border enforcement of titles⁷ in the laws of

¹ Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgements in civil and commercial matters (recast) 2012 (OJ L).

² Regulation (EC) No 805/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 creating a European Enforcement Order for uncontested claims 2004 (OJ L).

³ Regulation (EC) No 1896/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 creating a European order for payment procedure 2006 (OJ L).

⁴ Regulation (EC) No 861/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 establishing a European Small Claims Procedure 2007 (OJ L).

⁵ Regulation (EU) No 655/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 establishing a European Account Preservation Order procedure to facilitate cross-border debt recovery in civil and commercial matters 2014 (OJ L).

⁶ *Towards more Effective enFORcemenT of claimS in civil and commercial matters within the EU* (Project No JUST-JCOO-AG-2019- 881802). All the Project deliverables are freely accessible on the Project Website at <<https://efforts.unimi.it>>.

⁷ Specifically, the Brussels I bis Regulation, the EEO Regulation, and the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO Regulations.

seven EU Member States.⁸ While the data collected during the Project will serve as the primary basis for the analysis of the practical operation of harmonised EU procedures in the targeted Member States, some more general lessons on the overall state of EU judicial cooperation will also be drawn from this experience.

Hence, this contribution will be divided into four parts:

1. By way of introduction, the first part will provide an overview of the three European Regulations from a *functional perspective*, i.e., it will try to briefly describe what these procedures were meant to do and which scenarios they were designed to cover. By doing so, this part will provide some useful background about the Regulations' initial ambitions, and the actual challenges that have arisen from their application.
2. The second part will then briefly lay out some of the data collected in the course of the EFFORTS Project, thus giving a better sense of the current state of implementation of the three harmonised EU procedures in the seven Member States covered by the Project.
3. Building on this additional context, the third part will then delve deeper into the application of harmonised European procedures by focusing on a specific case study concerning the application of the EPO Regulation in France and Luxembourg, respectively.
4. Finally, the contribution will conclude by sharing some key takeaways on EU Procedures, as well as some outlooks on current developments in the area of judicial cooperation in civil and commercial matters within the EU.

1. INTRODUCTION: HARMONISED EU PROCEDURES FROM A FUNCTIONAL PERSPECTIVE

In order to assess the current state of application of the EPO, ESCP, and the EAPO Regulations, it is useful to take a look at these instruments from a functional perspective. What were these harmonised procedures supposed to

⁸ Namely: Belgium, Croatia, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, and Luxembourg.

do? Specifically, which kinds of cases were they designed to cover? The answers to these questions are important because, as we shall see immediately, the three Regulations actually address two very different scenarios.

A. Three Harmonised Procedures, Two Different Scenarios

From a strictly legal perspective, each harmonised EU procedure provides a different remedy to creditors engaged in cross-border litigation. On the one hand, the rules laid out in the EPO and ESCP Regulations set up two additional remedies for claimants who wish to accelerate the recovery of uncontested monetary claims⁹ or pursue the enforcement of small claims with a value of less than €5,000,¹⁰ respectively. On the other hand, the EAPO Regulation facilitates the cross-border recovery of debts by allowing creditors to secure their claims against bank accounts located in a Member State other than the Member State of the court seised on the merits or the Member State of the creditor's domicile.¹¹ From a functional point of view, however, all these procedures can be compared in that they have been designed to address two distinct scenarios, depending on the location of the parties and the ultimate configuration of the economic interests at stake.

1st Scenario: Facilitating the Circulation of Enforcement Titles

The first scenario reflects the situation in which a claim is brought before the courts of one Member State with a view to obtaining a judgment that can then be enforced in another Member State where the debtor's assets are located.

Historically, this scenario appears to have been the driving force behind the adoption of both the EPO and the ESCP Regulations, which were both introduced as part of the so-called 'Hague Programme' set up by the EU Council in order to expand the principle of mutual recognition of decisions between Member States and thus contribute to the strengthening the EU area of

⁹ See Regulation 1896/2006, Art 1.

¹⁰ See Regulation 861/2007, Arts 1–2.

¹¹ See Regulation 655/2014, Arts 1–3.

freedom, security, and justice.¹² Similarly, the adoption of the EAPO Regulation also appears to have been carried out in response to a similar concern, namely the exclusion of *ex parte* provisional and protective measures from the scope of the Brussels I bis Regulation.¹³

Technically, this scenario appears to have been addressed by all three Regulations (EPO, ESCP, and EAPO) by: (i) abolishing the exequatur procedure in the Member State of enforcement; (ii) reducing the grounds of refusal of enforcement (especially by excluding the public policy and due process defences); and (iii) shifting remedies from the Member State of enforcement to the Member State of origin whenever possible.

2nd Scenario: Providing Out-of-State Creditors Access to Local Courts

Following the adoption of the Brussels I bis Regulation and the general abolition of exequatur proceedings, the traditional test case for the application of harmonised EU procedures has been flanked by a second scenario.

Thanks to the harmonised nature of the rules laid out in the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO Regulation, out-of-State creditors may in fact be tempted to directly sue their debtors in the Member State where their assets are located, rather than having the courts of one Member State adjudicating the dispute on the merits and then seeking enforcement of the resulting title in another Member State.

In theory at least, several features of the EU Regulations make this option available to out-of-State creditors: (i) the use of standard forms which are available in all official EU languages and are identical across all Member States; (ii) a strong emphasis put on written procedures over oral hearings; (iii) the adoption of liberal rules on legal representation, which do not only allow

¹² Council of the European Union, ‘The Hague Programme: Strengthening Freedom, Security and Justice in the European Union’ (2005/C 053/1) para 3.4.2.

¹³ See Brussels I bis, Art 2(a); add also ECJ, Case 125/79 *Bernard Denilauler v SNC Couchet Frères* ECLI:EU:C:1980:130 [1980]. The EAPO Regulation partially fills this gap by allowing the courts of one State to issue an account preservation order targeting a bank account located in another Member State (see EAPO Regulation, Art 3(1)(a)).

creditors to file claims *pro se* but also—and most importantly—indirectly facilitate cross-border legal assistance from foreign-qualified attorneys.

B. Enduring Obstacles to the Adoption of Harmonised EU Procedures

Despite these ambitions, however, experience shows that several obstacles continue to hamper the smooth operation of the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO Regulations in practice. Indeed, so far the three harmonised EU procedures seem to have enjoyed only a limited success in most EU Member States, and several factors continue to undermine, albeit to a different extent, their widespread dissemination across the EU in each of the scenarios described above.

1st Scenario: Significant Overlaps in EU Civil and Commercial Judicial Cooperation

On the one hand, the application of these three instruments suffers from the significant overlaps which continue to exist in the field of EU civil judicial cooperation, and especially from the competition of the Brussels I bis and EEO Regulations, which also provide effective tools for creditors who wish to obtain a title to be enforced abroad. In this respect, several factors contribute to limit the use of harmonised EU procedures, especially after the generalisation of the abolition of *exequatur* proceedings.

Among these, the most important is probably the greater familiarity that practitioners have with the application of the Brussels I bis Regulation, which may work as an incentive for both in-State and out-of-State creditors to rely, whenever possible, on the generally applicable and more firmly established regime laid out in this Regulation rather than make use of the EPO, ESCP, or EAPO Regulations. Secondly, the application of the harmonised EU procedures may also be undermined by service issues, which affect in particular the interplay between the rules laid out in the Service Regulation¹⁴ and the

¹⁴ Regulation (EU) No 2020/1784 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2020 on the service in the Member States of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil or commercial matters (service of documents) (recast) 2020 (OJ L).

minimum standards and harmonised rules specifically crafted within the context of each harmonised procedure.¹⁵ Finally, the third element that can also adversely affect the widespread use of these procedures stems from the limited impact that the exclusion of the international public policy and due process exceptions have had in practice, especially in the field of monetary claims.

2nd Scenario: Persistent Reluctance to Make Use of EU Procedures in another Member State

On the other hand, some other factors also work as an obstacle to the generalisation of EU procedures under the second scenario, i.e., when these procedures are used as a way for foreign creditors to gain access to justice in another EU Member State.

Among these obstacles, the most important is undoubtedly the presence of a general and understandable preference for domestic procedures among national legal practitioners, which is often reinforced by the persistence of language and economic barriers among Member States. Indeed, a vast majority of European jurisdictions only accept standard forms that are filled out in the official language of the court seized.¹⁶ Similarly, court fees may vary significantly from one Member State to the other,¹⁷ a circumstance which might itself discourage parties to file a claim in another country. Finally, other legal,

¹⁵ On the issues that may arise in these regard, see most notably ECJ, Joined Cases C-119/13 and C-120/13 *eco cosmetics GmbH & Co KG and Raiffeisenbank St Georgen reg Gen mbH v Virginie Laetitia Barbara Dupuy and Tetyana Bonchyk* ECLI:EU:C:2014:2144; and Case C-21/17 *Catlin Europe SE v O K Trans Praha spol s r o* ECLI:EU:C:2018:675.

¹⁶ This appears to be the case in all the Member States covered by the EFFORTS Project.

¹⁷ For an overview of the considerable differences existing among Member States, see the dedicated sections on the e-Justice Portal: ‘European E-Justice Portal– Court Fees Concerning European Payment Order Procedure’ <https://e-justice.europa.eu/305/EN/court_fees_concerning_european_payment_order_procedure> accessed 30 April 2024 (EPO Regulation); ‘European E-Justice Portal– Court Fees Concerning Small Claims Procedure’ <https://e-justice.europa.eu/306/EN/court_fees_concerning_small_claims_procedure> accessed 30 April 2024 (ESCP Regulation); ‘European E-Justice Portal– European Account Preservation Order’ <https://e-justice.europa.eu/379/EN/european_account_preservation_order?clang=en> accessed 30 April 2024 (EAPO Regulation).

technical, and organisational hurdles, such as difficulties with the interpretation of domestic rules on subject-matter jurisdiction and venue¹⁸ or limited access to national IT networks of communication for out-of-State parties¹⁹ may have a dissuasive effect on creditors who would otherwise be willing to take advantage of harmonised European rules in order to sue their debtors domiciled in another Member State.

2. THE PROCEDURES IN PRACTICE: A SIGNIFICANTLY VARIED LANDSCAPE ACROSS MEMBER STATES

Against this general background, it might actually be helpful to take a closer look at some data collected during the EFFORTS Project in order to see what factors may actually have an impact on the practical application of harmonised EU procedures at the national level.

A. The Importance of National Implementing Rules

In general, the analysis of the implementation of the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO Regulations into national procedural law has revealed that the use of harmonised EU procedures is much less widespread in the Member States that have not adopted explicit national implementing rules within their domestic justice systems.²⁰

¹⁸ For a more in-depth analysis of such issues conducted within the context of EFFORTS, see M Buzzoni and C Santaló Goris, ‘Report on Practices in Comparative and Cross-Border Perspective’ (Max Planck Institute Luxembourg 2022) pp 43 ff <<https://hal.science/hal-04381239>> accessed 30 April 2024.

¹⁹ On the problems that may arise from the intersection between law and technology in this area, see in particular the judgement *Jean-Philippe Lahorgue v Ordre des avocats du barreau de Lyon and Others* [2017] ECJ Case C-99/16.

²⁰ On the importance of national implementing strategies, see in particular Q C Lobach, ‘The Effectiveness of the Regulations on Cross-Border Enforcement and National Implementing Rules’, in F C Villata and B Hess, ‘EFFORTS Final Study’ pp 55–62 <<https://efforts.unimi.it/research-outputs/final-study/>> accessed 30 April 2024; add M Buzzoni and others, ‘Report on EU Policy Guidelines’ (Max Planck Institute Luxembourg 2022) pp 22–6 <<https://hal.science/hal-04381321>> accessed 30 April 2024.

Fig. 1: National implementing rules by country (Source: EFFORTS Reports on National Implementing Rules, <<https://efforts.unimi.it/research-outputs/reports/collection-of-national-implementing-rules/>>)

In this respect, both the Belgian and Italian Reports underscore how uniform EU procedures are only rarely used in practice and still remain relatively unknown to many domestic legal professionals.²¹ The same observation holds true for countries such as France, where the absence of specific implementing rules for the EAPO Regulation has been reported as a significant factor for the very low number of applications filed each year under this Regulation before the French courts.²²

B. Improving Access to National Case Law

In the absence of explicit rules on harmonised EU procedures in several countries, a significant amount of research during the EFFORTS Project has been devoted to the study of national case law. Here, too, however, the situation

²¹ Buzzoni and others, *ibid* p 23.

²² On this aspect, see M Buzzoni and V Van Den Eeckhout, ‘Collection of French Implementing Rules’ (Max Planck Institute Luxembourg 2021) pp 59 ff <<https://hal.science/hal-04347694>> accessed 2 May 2024, and M Buzzoni, ‘Report on National Case Law’ (Max Planck Institute Luxembourg 2021) pp 99 ff <<https://hal.science/hal-04347718>> accessed 2 May 2024. According to data shared by the French Ministry of Justice, French courts only received 21 EAPO applications in 2021, 18 in 2022, and 14 in 2023.

varies greatly from one country to another, as you can see from the graph below.

Fig. 2: Number of court decisions collected by country (Source: EFFORTS Reports on National Case-Law, <<https://efforts.unimi.it/research-outputs/reports/collection-of-national-case-law/>>)

Naturally, these disparities do not directly reflect the actual use of the EPO, ESCP and EAPO Regulations in each of the Member States covered by the Project, since the data vary greatly according to the number of cases accessible through free and commercial databases. In this respect, one cannot overstate the benefits for empirical legal research that stem from a strong policy in favour of open access to court decisions.²³

On a very general level, we may also notice that, overall, harmonised EU procedures have so far given rise to a very limited number of reported decisions from the highest national courts. Especially when combined with a complete lack of guidance from national legislatures, this factor may also contribute to

²³ Since the end of the EFFORTS Project, it is important to note that several initiatives have been set up or implemented at the national level to increase the number of national decisions openly and freely accessible online. In time, these initiatives have the potential to significantly improve the quality and accuracy of empirical legal research.

explaining the reluctance of legal practitioners to abandon the use of national instruments in favour of relatively obscure provisions of EU law.

3. CASE STUDY: THE EPO PROCEDURE IN FRANCE AND LUXEMBOURG

Following this very general overview of the research conducted in the framework of the EFFORTS Project, the time has now come to delve deeper into a specific test case for the implementation of EU procedures at the national level, namely the application of the EPO Procedure in the French and Luxembourg legal systems.

A. Making Sense of the Numbers: A Look at National Data on EPO Applications

As the graph below shows, a quick comparison between the number of EPO applications received by the courts of France and Luxembourg immediately raises some interesting questions about the concrete implementation of the EPO Regulation into these two legal systems. Indeed, the number of EPO applications filed in both countries between 2020 and 2022 has remained relatively stable, varying between 426 (in 2020) and 489 (in 2022) in France and between 236 (in 2021) and 283 (in 2020) in Luxembourg.

Fig. 3: Yearly number of EPO applications filed before national courts (Source: France and Luxembourg Ministries of Justice)

Quite surprisingly, the number of EPO applications filed in Luxembourg (a country with fewer than 700,000 inhabitants) has received approximately 50 per cent of the number of EPOs registered by French civil courts (which has a population of more than 68,000,000).²⁴ At the outset, one may therefore come to the conclusion that the EPO Regulation has enjoyed much less success in France than in the Grand Duchy. This impression is also strengthened if one takes a peek at the situation in other neighbouring countries: in 2022, Belgian courts received 426 EPO applications for disputes above 5,000 euros,²⁵ while the number of EPO applications received each year by German courts has consistently been six to seven times higher than that of their French counterparts.²⁶

What factors might help to explain such differences between Member States which are all situated around the same borders and have all been part of the European family since 1957?

First of all, the comparison between France and Luxembourg might lead one to consider the relative weight of cross-border trade in the overall economy as a decisive factor in the attractiveness of the EPO Regulation. As a small, heavily financialised economy that is highly dependent on cross-border trade with its European neighbours, Luxembourg is naturally an ideal breeding ground for the application of EU instruments. However, this factor does not seem sufficient to explain why the number of applications filed with the EPO in France is significantly lower than in Germany and comparable to that of another smaller country such as Belgium.

Secondly, one could look at the presence and quality of national implementing rules to explain the disparate level of success between these countries. However, this approach would quickly lead to a dead end, as the French

²⁴ Unfortunately, the data collected by the French Ministry of Justice does not include EPOs filed before commercial courts.

²⁵ See the data published by the Belgian Ministry of Justice, available at ‘Statistiques | Cours & Tribunaux’ <<https://www.rechtbanken-tribunaux.be/fr/statistiques>> accessed 30 April 2024.

²⁶ According to the data collected by the *Amtsgericht Wedding*, which acts as the centralised court for payment order procedures (*Zentrales Mahngericht*), there were a total of 2,857 and 3,401 yearly EPO applications filed in Germany in 2022 and 2023, respectively.

legislature has adopted a clear and comprehensive set of implementing rules for the EPO Regulation, contrary to many other EU Member States.²⁷

Thirdly, another factor often cited as a major contributor to the adoption of the EPO Regulation is the concentration of proceedings before a single specialised court, as well as the possibility of filing applications electronically. However, of the countries cited in our brief survey, only Germany appears to process EPO applications according to these principles. Albeit important, concentration and digitalisation alone cannot therefore explain the comparison between Belgium, France, and Luxembourg.

In order to explain the different levels of adoption of the EPO procedure in these countries, it is therefore necessary to look beyond the application of this Regulation alone. Indeed, the research carried out as part of the EFFORTS project has highlighted what is probably the most significant difference between these Member States, namely the availability (or lack thereof) of effective and affordable national alternatives to the EPO in the national legal system. Indeed, national payment orders do not exist (or are less creditor-friendly than the EPO procedure) in Belgium,²⁸ Germany²⁹ and Luxembourg,³⁰ particularly when the debtor's domicile is in another Member State, whereas this option is available in France according to the French courts' understanding of their own jurisdiction.³¹ This last circumstance therefore allows French creditors to apply for a national order for payment and then, if necessary, enforce their title under the EEO or the Brussels I bis Regulation, rather than using the relatively unknown rules of the EPO Regulation.

These brief considerations on the application of the EPO procedure in several Member States covered by the EFFORTS Project already show the value of comparative research for understanding the practical operation of EU instruments in the field of civil judicial cooperation. However, a study of the concrete functioning of this Regulation between France and Luxembourg

²⁷ See *supra*, fig. 1.

²⁸ See Belgian Judicial Code ('Code judiciaire'), Arts 1338–1344.

²⁹ See German Code of Civil Procedure ('ZPO'), §§ 688 ff.

³⁰ See Luxembourg Code of Civil Procedure ('Nouveau code de procédure civile'), Art 129 ff.

³¹ See French Code of Civil Procedure ('Code de procédure civile'), Arts 1405–1424.

would not be complete without a more detailed analysis of the flows that take place at the border between these two countries.

B. A Success Story: The Use of the EPO Regulation at the French-Luxembourg Border

Irrespective of the presence of effective domestic equivalents to the EPO procedure, this Regulation has indeed proven to be a particularly useful tool of redress for Luxembourg creditors seeking to collect monetary claims before French domestic courts. As the graph below shows, the percentage of EPO applications filed before the Thionville and Metz border courts has in fact counted for around 20 per cent of the overall number of EPO applications in France between 2020 and 2022.

Fig. 4: Percentage of EPO applications filed in Thionville and Metz compared to the rest of France (Source: French Ministry of Justice)

Furthermore, according to data published by the French Ministry of Justice in 2019,³² the number of EPO applications filed before the same courts between 2012 and 2019 represented approximately 25 per cent of the national total. Perhaps even more impressively, the same survey also revealed that the

³²Z Belmokhtar and C Kissoun-Faujas, 'Les injonctions de payer en 2019: de la demande à l'opposition' (2020) No 178 <<https://www.justice.gouv.fr/documentation/etudes-et-statistiques/injonctions-payer-2019-demande-lopposition>> accessed 30 April 2024.

number of EPO applications filed by Luxembourg plaintiffs all over France amounted to a staggering 41 per cent percent of the total number of EPO applications filed by out-of-State plaintiffs during that year.³³

Taken together, these figures confirm that harmonised EU procedures may represent a particularly effective tool for out-of-State creditors against in-State defendants, provided, however, that some very important conditions are met.

First of all, the successful application of the EPO Regulation at the French-Luxembourg border seems to be premised on the presence of minimal friction due to the absence of linguistic and economic barriers (indeed, France and Luxembourg share a common legal language, and there are no legal costs in French civil courts).

Secondly, the presence of a clear legal framework governing the implementation of the EPO Regulation in French national law certainly generates a good level of confidence among Luxembourg legal practitioners, which is also favoured by the fact that many practising lawyers in Luxembourg have received at least part of their legal training in France.

Thirdly, the fact that Luxembourg lawyers are already accustomed to applying the EPO Regulation in their home State due to the absence of a perfect substitute in their national law ensures a good level of familiarity with EU procedural rules among the practitioners concerned. At the same time, the presence of a healthy stream of applications directed to French courts situated in the north-eastern part of the country also contribute to building capacity on this side of the border.

4. CONCLUSIONS: FROM DIRECT ENFORCEMENT TO ENHANCED ACCESS TO JUSTICE FOR OUT-OF-STATE PARTIES?

Based on this quick overview of the main scenarios in which the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO procedures may be used, and thanks to the specific examples that we have unearthed so far, it is now possible to lay out some key takeaways and future outlooks for the development of harmonised EU procedures. In this

³³ Ibid.

regard, our analysis naturally leads to two very different (though not mutually exclusive) approaches to increase the attractiveness of EU harmonised procedures.

A. Rationalising the EU Judicial Cooperation Landscape of Cross-Border Enforcement

In light of the significant overlaps resulting from the rapid accumulation of European Regulations that have crowded the space of transnational debt recovery over the past two decades, a first possible approach to the problem of poor implementation and lack of awareness of harmonised EU procedures could be a (more or less) radical rationalisation of the EU judicial cooperation landscape. In particular, eminent authors have recently taken a stand in favour of this approach, emphasising in particular the systemic impact of the general abolition of *exequatur* introduced by the Brussels I bis Regulation.

In practice, the first measure that is frequently proposed when it comes to the simplification of the EU judicial cooperation landscape concerns the abrogation of the EEO Regulation,³⁴ which is often presented as a redundant alternative to the Brussels I bis and EPO Regulation when it comes to the cross-border collection of uncontested monetary claims,³⁵ and which might expose the debtor to parallel enforcement attempts on the territory of several Member States.³⁶

A second, even more radical measure, which has also been touted as a way to simplify the EU judicial cooperation landscape, would consist in the pure and simple exclusion of national orders for payment from the scope of the Brussels I bis Regulation.³⁷ This proposal follows the same model that has been *de facto* endorsed with the introduction of the EAPO Regulation following the exclusion

³⁴ See eg B Hess and others, ‘The Reform of the Brussels Ibis Regulation’ (15 November 2022) 30 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4278741>> accessed 15 March 2024.

³⁵ See Buzzoni and others (n 20) p 17.

³⁶ On this danger, see B Hess, *Europäisches Zivilprozessrecht* (2nd edn, De Gruyter 2021) paras 6.40–1.

³⁷ In favour of excluding domestic order for payment procedures in cross-border cases, see B Hess, ‘Re-Recasting Brussels I-Bis’ in FC Villata and B Hess, ‘EFFORTS Final Study’ p 131 <<https://efforts.unimi.it/research-outputs/final-study/>> accessed 30 April 2024.

of *ex parte* provisional measures from the simplified enforcement rules of the Brussels I bis regime.

Finally, a third possible way to address the problem of mutual encroachment of EU instruments on the recovery of cross-border claims would be to make EU harmonised procedures mandatory in certain circumstances, for example for cross-border claims worth less than 5,000 euros or for orders for payment against defendants domiciled abroad.

With the possible exception of the abolition of the EEO Regulation,³⁸ all these proposals have the considerable disadvantage of reducing the number of solutions available to ensure the effective protection of claims in cross-border civil proceedings and a smooth circulation of titles across Member States. Indeed, by advocating the removal of a number of legal relationships from the scope of the existing instruments, these measures embody a ‘negative’ approach which, while likely to increase the use of EU harmonised procedures compared to the Brussels I bis Regulation and the EEO Regulation, could ultimately result in a zero-sum game between the existing Regulations rather than enhance the overall use of EU judicial cooperation tools.

B. Embracing the Specificities of Harmonised EU Procedures as a Way to Enhance Access to Justice Beyond Borders

Rather than merely focusing on the rationalisation of the EU dispute resolution landscape, we therefore argue that a more palatable policy programme for EU policy-makers should consider embracing a more ‘positive’ approach, which would foster the complementarity between EU instruments of judicial cooperation while also encouraging their widespread adoption across the board. In our view, such approach should priorities reforms of harmonised EU procedures aimed at further empowering out-of-State creditors to directly sue their debtors in the Member State where their assets are located. By doing so, the EU legislature would therefore strengthen the specificity of the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO procedures vis-à-vis the Brussels I bis and EEO Regulations

³⁸ See Buzzoni and others (n 20) pp 16–17, arguing that ‘the development of the European instruments allowing for the direct enforcement of titles across Member States has simply outgrown the provisions of the EEO Regulation’.

without reducing the range of remedies available to creditors in cross-border cases. In order for the EPO, ESCP, and EAPO Regulations to become a credible and effective option in this regard, however, further steps seem necessary to overcome some of the practical difficulties we have highlighted above.

First of all, additional efforts at the Member States level are urgently needed to lower language barriers across the EU. To be clear, this observation should not be taken as an unrealistic call for a blanket adoption of multilingualism before courts throughout the EU, nor for the endorsement of futuristic real-time translation tools, which might themselves pose their own legal, economic, and organisational challenges. Much more modestly, one could nevertheless draw inspiration, at least for a number of disputes selected on the basis of specific characteristics, from the considerable experience that several Member States have now developed with the establishment of English-speaking commercial courts specialised in cross-border dispute resolution.³⁹

Secondly, the legislative initiatives recently undertaken by the European Commission on the digitisation of EU judicial cooperation⁴⁰ clearly represent an enormous potential for the development of harmonised procedures, as the establishment of a single Europe-wide electronic access point⁴¹ promises to further reduce the costs and delays associated with cross-border civil and commercial litigation. At the same time, it is important to note that such results will still require significant coordination and implementation work at both European and Member State levels, without which the newly digitised

³⁹ On the interplay between the development of international commercial courts and EU law, see recently P Ortolani and B Van Zelst, 'International Commercial Courts and EU Law: Easing the Tension' (2023) 14 *Journal of International Dispute Settlement* 76.

⁴⁰ With respect to EU judicial cooperation in civil and commercial matters, see in particular Regulation (EU) 2023/2844 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on the digitalisation of judicial cooperation and access to justice in cross-border civil, commercial and criminal matters, and amending certain acts in the field of judicial cooperation 2023, as well as Regulation (EU) 2022/850 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on a computerised system for the cross-border electronic exchange of data in the area of judicial cooperation in civil and criminal matters (e-CODEX system), and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1726.

⁴¹ See Regulation (EU) 2023/2844, Art 4.

European procedures will be unable to hold their weight against their national counterparts.

Thirdly, any future legislative efforts in this area should focus on minimising European fragmentation by ensuring that the numerous references to national law still present in the EU Regulations establishing harmonised EU procedures do not lead to unequal levels of protection for EU citizens across the Member States, but also that the rules of judicial cooperation laid down in these instruments are consistent with other areas of EU law.⁴²

As this very brief overview of the policy options available hopefully shows, the fact that EU instruments now cover virtually all areas of judicial cooperation in civil matters still leaves considerable headroom for improvement in the European area of freedom, security and justice. And while digitisation undoubtedly represents a new frontier in this respect, it in no way diminishes the need to further refine our understanding of how EU law works in practice through critical, evidence-based academic research in the field of private international law and cross-border civil procedure.

⁴² On such efforts, see Buzzoni and others (n 20) pp 21 ff.